

Electrochemical Studies on Some Sulphonamoylazopyrazoles

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Manuscript received 30 July 1997, revised 18 February 1998, accepted 27 February 1998

The electrochemical reduction of 1-nitrophenyl-3-aminophenyl-5-methyl-4-(4'-sulphonamoyl)azopyrazoles has been studied over a wide pH range at dropping mercury and glassy carbon electrodes. The compounds give one four-electron wave corresponding to the reduction of nitro group, and one two-electron wave corresponding to the reduction of N=N group. On the basis of polarography, cyclic voltammetry, coulometry and controlled potential electrolysis, a reaction mechanism, has been suggested to account for the reduction mechanism.

Electrochemical reduction of aromatic azo compounds has been studied by various workers¹. Mabrouk *et al.*² found that in aqueous solutions of pH 3.5 nitroazo compounds are reduced at d.m.e. through four-electron diffusion-controlled irreversible wave. According to them the first wave represents the reduction of the easily reducible NO₂ group to NHOH stage and second wave is due to the reduction of N=N group. The voltammograms of these compounds at different sweep rate show two peaks in the cathodic scan in acidic or alkaline solutions, corresponding to two different reduction steps. However, there are only a few electrochemical studies dealing with heterocyclic azo compounds particularly at solid electrodes. In this communication, a comprehensive study has been undertaken on the electrochemical behaviour of newly synthesized nitrazo compounds bearing bulky pyrazole group at one of the nitrogen atoms of the azo group and sulphonamoyl moiety on the other nitrogen atom. In view of the broad spectrum bacteriocidal nature of sulphonamides, it was considered useful to study redox behaviour of some of the azo derivatives.

Results and Discussion

Polarograms of 1-nitrophenyl-3-aminophenyl-5-methyl-4-(4'-sulphonamoyl)azopyrazoles were recorded in the pH range 2.3–12.3. All aryl azopyrazoles exhibited two well-defined polarographic waves in the pH range 2.3 to 7.7. Although aryl azopyrazoles contain cyclic –C=C– and –C=N– bonds, but the –N=N– and –NO₂ groups are more susceptible to reduction because of their extra-nuclear position³. Out of the two waves, the first four-electron wave has been assigned to the reduction of NO₂ group by comparing with analogous compound. The second two-electron wave has been assigned to the reduction of azo group. Because of the closeness of half-wave potential of azo and nitro groups, both waves merged at higher pH and a single six-electron wave was realised. However, in CV both the peaks were clear and distinction is discernible at all pH values. Some typical voltammograms are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Some typical voltammograms of 1-nitrophenyl-3-aminophenyl-5-methyl-4- (1) (4'-pyrimidinylsulphonamoyl), (2) (4'-guanylsulphonamoyl)azopyrazole; pH = 10.1, concn. = 2.0×10^{-4} M.

Behaviour at DME :

Reduction of nitro group : Nitro group is easily reducible in aliphatic as well as in aromatic compounds⁴. The reduction of nitro group may take place to hydroxylamine (NHOH) in a four-electron process. For the formation of amine from NO₂ group six electrons are required in the reduction process, but aryl azopyrazoles under investigation consumed four electrons for the reduction of NO₂ group, and this shows that the NO₂ group is reduced to hydroxylamine. The plot of i_d vs \sqrt{h} , and i_d vs concentration show the diffusion-controlled nature of limiting current. The shift of $E_{1/2}$ towards more negative side with increasing concentration of depolariser and logarithmic analysis confirmed the irreversible nature of the electrode process⁵.

Reduction of azo group : The second two-electron wave has been assigned to the reduction of azo group by comparing it with the model compound not having NO₂ group. The shift of $E_{1/2}$ towards more negative potential with increase in pH of the medium indicates that protons are involved in the reduction process. The shift in $E_{1/2}$ towards more negative side is marked up to pH 7.7, thereafter, there is little shift in the $E_{1/2}$ towards more negative side with

increase in pH of the medium. The direct dependence of limiting current on the height of mercury column and concentration of depolariser suggests the diffusion-controlled nature of the electrode process. And the shift of $E_{1/2}$ towards more negative side with increase in pH and logarithmic analysis show the irreversible nature of electrode process.

The value of α_n (product of transfer coefficient and number of electrons involved per molecule of the reactant) and p (number of protons involved per molecule) in the rate-determining step were calculated using the expression,

$$\alpha_n = -0.0517/(E_{3/4} - E_{1/4})$$

$$p = dE_{1/2}/dpH (\alpha_n/0.0591)$$

Azo group is reduced in a two electron step to hydrazo group (-NH-NH-), and comparison of limiting current shows that most of the compounds are reduced by same number of electrons (Table 1).

Behaviour at GC electrode: Cyclic voltammograms of aryl azopyrazoles in buffer solutions of different acidity at

TABLE 1-POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF 1-NITROPHENYL-3-AMINOPHENYL-5-METHYL-4-(4'-SULPHONAMOYL)AZOPYRAZOLES
pH = 7.7, concn. = 2.0×10^{-4} M

Sl. no.	R	$-E_{1/2}$ V	$i_d, \mu A$	$\frac{dE_{1/2}}{dpH}$ V/pH	n	$I \times 10^2$	p
1.	H	0.64	0.78	0.86	0.08	8.15	1.1
2.		0.68	0.62	0.90	0.07	6.48	1.0
3.		0.70	0.74	0.98	0.07	7.73	1.1
4.		0.68	0.76	0.79	0.07	7.94	0.03
5.		1.10	0.68	0.88	0.04	7.10	0.91
6.		0.78	0.66	0.89	0.06	6.90	0.90

different sweep rates (50–250 mV/s) exhibited two peaks in the cathodic scan and no anodic peak in the reverse scan could be realised (Table 2). The first peak has been assigned to the reduction of nitro group. The linear plots of E_p vs $\nu^{1/2}$ shows the irreversible nature of the electrode process, and the plot of i_p vs concentration shows the diffusion-controlled nature⁶. Absence of anodic peak in the reverse scan also indicates the irreversible nature of the electrode process. The second two-electron peak has been assigned to the reduction of azo group to hydrazo group (-NH-NH-). The irreversible nature and diffusion-controlled nature of the reduction process were deduced by the shift of E_p towards more negative side with increase in scan rate (ν) and increase in peak current with the increase in concentration of the depolariser respectively. The irreversible nature of the electrode process for the reduction of azo group (in contrast to the behaviour of azo benzene) observed for these compounds may be due to the bulky pyrazole substituent present at one of the nitrogens of the azo group.

Controlled potential electrolysis and coulometry: Controlled potential electrolysis was carried out at a potential -0.8 V, slightly higher than the reduction potential of second peak, i.e. for azo group, and the number of electrons consumed in the average electrode process was found to be 6. Only one product could be identified after working up the solution obtained after controlled potential electrolysis. Products were separated by tlc and identified by elemental and spectral analysis. The product gave negative dye test, indicating that NO_2 group is reduced to -NH-NH-.

Reduction mechanism: Based on the results of polarography, cyclic voltammetry⁷, coulometry and controlled potential electrolysis, the suggested reduction mechanism for 1-nitrophenyl-3-aminophenyl-5-methyl-4-(4'-sulphoamoyl)azopyrazole is shown in Scheme 1.

Similar steps for reduction of azo group have also been reported by other workers⁸.

TABLE 2-VALUES OF PEAK POTENTIALS (V)* FOR 1-NITROPHENYL-3-AMINOPHENYL-5-METHYL-4-(4'-SULPHONAMOYL)AZOPYRAZOLES AT DIFFERENT pH

Concn. = 2.0×10^{-4} M

Sl no.**	pH 2.3		4.2		7.7		10.1		11.4		12.3	
	E_{p_1}	E_{p_2}										
1.	0.24	0.50	0.28	0.56	0.36	0.73	0.37	0.74	0.38	0.75	0.38	0.75
2.	0.36	0.52	0.38	0.56	0.41	0.68	0.42	0.72	0.43	0.71	0.43	0.72
3.	0.31	0.55	0.34	0.60	0.39	0.66	0.40	0.67	0.40	0.67	0.41	0.69
4.	0.31	0.53	0.34	0.56	0.39	0.65	0.40	0.65	0.41	0.64	0.42	0.66
5.	0.42	0.90	0.47	0.95	0.53	1.08	0.52	1.14	0.56	1.20	0.56	1.20
6.	0.27	0.61	0.29	0.66	0.36	0.76	0.35	0.78	0.37	0.78	0.37	0.79

* E_{p_1} (V) is for the reduction of nitro group. **Compounds refer to as Sl. nos. in Table 1.

Scheme 1

Effect of ionic strength : To study the effect of ionic strength on the $E_{1/2}$ of process, the polarograms of 1-nitrophenyl-3-aminophenyl-5-methyl-4-(4'-pyrimidinyl sulphonamoyl)azopyrazole were recorded in different molarity of KCl (0.5–2.5 M) at pH 9.6. The values of $E_{1/2}$ and diffusion current remained constant at different strengths of KCl, as observed by other workers^{9,10}.

Effect of cations and anions : The effect of size of cat-

ion and anion on the polarographic wave for the reduction of 1-nitrophenyl-3-aminophenyl-5-methyl-4-(4'-pyrimidinyl sulphonamoyl)azopyrazole was studied in molar solutions of LiCl, NaCl, KCl, KSCN, KI as supporting electrolyte.

The $E_{1/2}$ shifted towards more negative potential with the increase in the size of cation without influencing wave-height. The increase in the size of cation results in the increase in ψ (variation in double layer potential), leading to more difficult reduction, and therefore $E_{1/2}$ shifts towards more negative side. Further studies were made in supporting electrolytes having common cation and different anions. However, no change in $E_{1/2}$ and i_d was observed, as cation predominates in the electrical double layer at these potentials.

Experimental

1-Nitrophenyl-3-aminophenyl-5-methyl-4-(4'-sulphonamoyl)azopyrazoles were prepared by the developed method. The compounds were purified by repeated crystallization and the purity was checked by tlc.

Polarograms were recorded on an Elico CL-25 polarograph. Potentiometric studies were carried out on a DP510 pH meter with glass electrodes. Voltammograms were recorded on a BAS CV-27 cyclic voltammograph using a 2000 Omnigraph x-y/t recorder. The details have been reported elsewhere¹⁰.

Solutions (2.0×10^{-3} M) of all the compounds were prepared in purified DMF (A.R.). A 1.0 M KCl (A.R.) was used as the supporting electrolyte. B.R. buffers¹¹ of different pH were used to evaluate the effect of acidity.

For preparing the solutions for polarographic studies, 1.0 ml of depolariser, 2.0 ml of DMF, 1.0 ml of KCl and 6.0 ml of appropriate B.R. buffer and solutions of similar composition were also used for C.V.¹⁰.

Controlled potential electrolysis and identification of end-products : CPE at d.m.e. and GC electrode was done in a micro-cell. For this purpose, a solution of the depolariser (2.0 ml), B.R. buffer (4.0 ml), DMF (3.0 ml) and KCl (1.0 ml) was electrolysed at a potential on the limiting current plateau of the wave. Number of electrons involved in the electrode process were also evaluated by coulometry and CPE. Value of Q was read directly and by using following formula number of electrons 'n' were calculated : $Q = nFN$.

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